

The impact of robot communication style on user task performance

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Abstract—Humans naturally hold conversations and interact swiftly with each other, conveying content and biases (un)consciously with verbal and non-verbal communication. This phenomenon is inherently shipped with social robots, whose tasks include interacting with people verbally and eventually helping them to complete a task. To understand the impact of verbal and non-verbal communication on the task at hand, we built a game scenario and endowed a social robot with two clearly distinguishable communication styles. The user study allowed us to understand how the communication style of the robot can impact task performance and shed some light on its gradient. Additionally, our results show that participants with lower prior experience with robots obtained higher game scores, suggesting a shift of interest of experienced participants in the communication strategies of the robot rather than in the game.

Index Terms—Social Robotics, Communication Styles, Game Scenario

I. INTRODUCTION

The gamification of Human-Robot Interaction (HRI) allows researchers to conduct scripted interactions while controlling only for limited variables. This facilitates user studies as participants might be familiar with the game at hand but unfamiliar with the robot’s behaviour. Despite the underlying objectives of different researchers, similar approaches have been used in [1], where the scenario involved a chess game or in [2] where the game was designed to maintain user motivation during the experiment.

With the increasing frequency of social interactions that robots are called to perform, it is important to understand if the way robots communicate with humans can influence their task performances or even shape their decision-making strategies. When users are performing a task with the support or involvement of a robot, it is natural to expect a robot’s feedback on the interaction or the task. In such cases, a robot that employs authoritative or aggressive feedback might discourage the user from continuing the task or even be emotionally hurtful. However, an authoritative robot communication style might be preferred in limited use cases as depicted in [3].

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Fig. 1. Participant plays the game with the assistance of the ARI robot.

Nonetheless, it is well established that positive robot feedback is preferred when conducting task-based HRIs. For instance, Andriella et al. [4] and Paetzel et al. [5] found that users’ performance improved when participants interacted with a robot endowed with a polite interaction style compared to those who interacted with a provocative and challenging one.

Regarding whether robot communication style can impact user decision-making, it is not yet established the extent of the effect if there is one. For instance, a robot could encourage a human to adopt healthier habits [6] or motivate an older adult to do cognitive and physical exercises [7].

Here, we extend the discussion of the work presented in [8], in which the social robot ARI¹ plays a game with humans and is endowed with two communication styles (CS), namely: *agreeable* and *antagonistic*. These are implemented as multi-modal behaviours displayed by the robot on its turn during the quiz game and are highly characterised by the robot’s speech content (see Table I in [8]). The code for reproducing the study is available².

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²https://github.com/Prisca-Lab/robot_quiz

II. DISCUSSION

The game is made of four closed-answer questions that the robot is presenting to the participant involved in the game. The participant is given a wireless microphone and a headset for the interaction and can respond to the robot's question in three different ways:

- 1) Choose one of the four available answers;
- 2) Request a hint from the robot, hence removing two of the wrong options from the answers;
- 3) Ask the robot to repeat the question;

During the game, the robot is sequentially presenting a set of questions to the participant, each paired with four possible answers. Depending on the participants' choice the robot could display its communication style upon the user's response. In case the user asked to repeat the question, the robot feedback was not characterised by the *agreeable* or *antagonistic* communication style.

After presenting all the questions, the robot attempts to influence participant decision-making cognitively and physically. We invite the reader to read [8] for a thorough overview of the study.

A. The study

Sixty-six (66) adults interacted with the robot employing either an *agreeable* or *antagonistic* communication style. The key results of the study are that:

- (i) participants that interacted with the *agreeable* robot obtained higher game scores wrt to those that interacted with the *antagonistic* one;
- (ii) participants' decision-making was not affected by the robot communication style;
- (iii) participants with higher previous experience with robots obtained lower game scores;

Regarding (i), our study reinforces the results of works like [4] and [5], in which a robot providing positive feedback influenced the task or game performance positively.

When designing social robots to engage users in a task, we recommend maintaining the same communication style across the whole population that is interacting with the robot. With this approach, the researcher can compare the task performance of the participants and be aware that a positive or negative robot communication style can shape the game score significantly.

It is also important to remark that despite the designed communication style being correctly distinguished (see **H1** in [8]) and a control condition is intentionally skipped, i.e., no robot feedback after user response, the results from (ii) suggest that participants' decision-making is not significantly influenced by robot communication style.

B. Participants impressions

Among the participants that interacted with the *antagonistic* robot, a participant stated that the robot "kind of annoyed me when it compared me to others who had guessed all the answers", while another participant stated that the robot "was

disturbing in certain moments". This group of participants was also the one that performed worst in the game and similar results are reported [4].

Among the participants that interacted with the *agreeable* robot, one participant found the robot to be pleasant and fun to play with, while another participant stated that the robot "is fun and useful". These responses could be linked to the Perceived Enjoyment [9], as in [4], however, this information was not collected during the study.

Considering (iii), we run a multi-linear regression model on the quiz scores having as predictors the communication style and user experience with the robot. It was found that the game scores of participants with lower experience with robots are overall higher wrt to the ones of participants with higher experience with robots.

This result can be explained by the intrinsic motivation of inexperienced participants to indeed play the game, while the more experienced ones might have been more interested in challenging the robot dialogue.

In future works, we plan to replicate the study with a more capillary investigation on prior experience with robots, i.e. distinguishing physical from virtual prior interactions.

Finally, it would be interesting to fragment the degree of *antagonism* and *agreeableness* in the robot communication style in order to get a more refined picture of how humans perceive social robot behaviours.

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